

PRIN 2022 RESIST

DELIVERABLE 5000-A

28-02-2025

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

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Summary

1. INTRODUCTION.....	3
2. THE EXPERIMENTAL PLANT FUNCTIONING AND OPERATORS' ACTIVITIES	3
2.1. The experimental plant.....	3
3. THE DIGITAL TWINS REALIZATION AND THEIR INTEGRATION	8
3.1. Cyber-Physical digital twin modelling	8
3.2. Human digital twin modelling.....	9
3.2.1 Motion capture technology	9
3.2.2 Recording campaign	9
3.2.3 Data analysis tool.....	10
3.2.4 Human digital twin from single actions.....	11
3.3. The Human-Hardware-in-the-Loop digital twin	12
4. THE ANALYZED CRITICAL SCENARIOS.....	13
4.1. The experimental plant DT critical scenarios simulation with no integration	14
4.1.1. Scenario 1	14
4.1.2. Scenario 2	18
4.2. The plant operator's DT scenarios simulation with no integration.....	22
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT.....	29

1. INTRODUCTION

The integration of the Digital Twins (DTs) of the experimental plant and the operator working within it is a crucial step toward creating an intelligent industrial system capable of real-time monitoring, optimization, and performance prediction. The DT of the plant provides an accurate digital replica of the processes and machines, enabling the analysis of variables such as efficiency, anomalies, and operational flows. Simultaneously, the digital twin of the operator simulates the interactions between the human and the machine, monitoring activities, decisions, and individual performance. Integrating these two models offers a comprehensive and dynamic view of the work environment, enhancing operational efficiency, safety, and the adoption of predictive strategies. This document explores the integration process, outlining the technologies involved and the methodologies employed.

2. THE EXPERIMENTAL PLANT FUNCTIONING AND OPERATORS' ACTIVITIES

2.1. The experimental plant

The plant examined is a lab prototype located within the Department of Industrial Engineering and Mathematical Sciences (DIISM) at the Università Politecnica delle Marche (Ancona, Italy). It was built in the early 1990s to artificially reproduce the extraction of natural gas from a depleted well using the oil in pressure of an active oil. As shown in Figure 1, to avoid the high costs associated to installing pumps at the bottom of reservoirs where internal pressure is insufficient to naturally surface oil and gas, a technique was developed that utilizes an ejector, leveraging the pressure from an adjacent active well.

For safety reasons, the experimental plant uses water and air at room temperature instead of crude oil and natural gas. The current configuration, which has been modified over the years, is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. An example of the experimental plant system.

Figure 2. The current experimental plant configuration.

As mentioned before, the plant replicates a typical extraction scenario where the pressure from a high-pressure reservoir is utilized to create suction in a reservoir with insufficient pressure for transport. In actual operations, crude oil and natural gas are the primary fluids, whereas the experimental setup uses water and air. In the oil, chemical, and nuclear industries, transporting two-phase gas-liquid mixtures through a single pipeline is a common challenge. Specifically in the oil sector, it is often the case that the pressure in an oil field isn't adequate to bring the oil to the surface. The conventional solution is to install pumps at the surface and the bottom of the well. However, a more efficient method involves using a higher-pressure neighboring well. Gas-liquid ejectors can combine two phases at different pressures and provide the required transport energy. These ejectors are advantageous due to their lack of moving parts, simplicity, low maintenance and installation costs, and the absence of sealing issues, making them suitable for transporting hydrocarbon mixtures and corrosive, toxic, or radioactive gases. Figure 3 shows the main components equipped on the plant in terms of sensors and solenoid valves, which are explained in detail in .

The pump connected to the open tank draws a water flow and sends it to the ejector at a specified pressure through the inlet water line (Figure 2). The water pressure is regulated by a solenoid valve (AV1 in Figure 3). Within the ejector, pressure energy is transformed into kinetic energy. This transformation creates a vacuum that draws in airflow from the outside at atmospheric pressure through the inlet airline (red line in Figure 2). In the final section, the two-phase mixture formed at the ejector outlet enters a vertical pressure tank, which serves as a vertical separator for the liquid and gaseous components through the inlet mixture line (black and yellow lines in Figure 2). In this part of the plant, the other two solenoid valves (AV2 and AV3 in Figure 3) control the water flow and airflow at the outlet through the outlet water and air lines, respectively; this system regulates the pressure and liquid level inside the tank.

Figure 3. The current experimental plant configuration with main components highlighted.

Table 1 – Description of main components equipped on the plant

ID	Description	Unit	Component name
S1	Inlet water pressure sensor	[bar]	Endress+ Hauser Cerabar M PMP51
S2	Inlet water flow rate sensor	[m ³ /h]	Endress+ Hauser Promag W
S3	Ejector pressure sensor	[bar]	Setra 280°
S4	Diffuser pressure sensor	[bar]	Foxboro 841GM CII
S5	Tank pressure sensor	[bar]	Endress+ Hauser Promag W
S6	Tank water level sensor	[mm]	Foxboro IDP-10
S7	Inlet air flow rate	[m ³ /h]	Foxboro Vortez DN 50
S8	Outlet air flow rate	[m ³ /h]	Endress+ Hauser Cerabar M PMP51
AV1	Inlet water pressure valve	% of closure	Spirax Sarco 9126E
AV2	Tank water level valve	% of closure	Eckardt MB6713
AV3	Tank pressure valve	% of closure	Eckardt MB6713

2.2. The plant operators' activities

An operator working in the described plant setup is responsible for monitoring and controlling various critical operations to ensure the proper functioning of the system. Key tasks include:

1. *Pressure Regulation*: the operator must adjust the solenoid valve (AV1) to regulate the water pressure entering the ejector. This is essential for maintaining the required vacuum pressure at the ejector and ensuring efficient gas-liquid mixture formation;
2. *Monitoring Fluid Flows*: the operator monitors the water and air flows through the respective inlet and outlet lines. They ensure that the flow rates are within optimal ranges and can adjust the

solenoid valves (AV2 and AV3) to regulate these flows, maintaining the correct pressure and liquid levels in the vertical pressure tank;

3. Ejector Operation: the operator oversees the performance of the ejector, which converts pressure energy into kinetic energy. They monitor the vacuum levels and ensure that the two-phase mixture is drawn in and transported effectively;
4. System Maintenance: Regular inspections of the plant's components, including the ejector, valves, and pumps, are necessary. the operator checks for any issues such as leaks, blockages, or performance drops and initiates troubleshooting procedures as needed;
5. Safety and Emergency Procedures: the operator must be familiar with emergency protocols, including the safe shutdown of equipment in case of system malfunctions, and ensuring that safety features are properly activated in response to abnormal conditions such as pressure surges or system failure;
6. Data Logging and Reporting: the operator records system data such as pressure, flow rates, and temperatures, which are used for monitoring system health and ensuring compliance with operational parameters. This data may be used for further analysis, diagnostics, or performance optimization.

By carrying out these operations, the operator ensures the plant operates efficiently, safely, and within the designed performance parameters.

2.3. The user interface for the plant management

Figure 4 illustrates the communication structure of the experimental plant, which integrates multiple sensors and control valves to regulate water flow, pressure, and levels. The system components, including sensors and valves, are detailed in Table 1. At the heart of the system is the Revolution Pi Core 3 (RevPi), serving as the data acquisition and control device. The RevPi Core 3+ features a Broadcom BCM2837B0 processor with a quad-core ARM Cortex-A53 running at 1.2 GHz, supported by 1 GB of DDR2 RAM. It interfaces with sensors and actuators, enabling real-time monitoring and adjustments via a command console. The system control interface, shown on the right side of the diagram, provides real-time visualization of sensor readings via both gauges and graphs. Figure 5 illustrates the complete user interface. Communication between the RevPi and the user interface occurs through an MQTT broker, utilizing the publish-subscribe model. The RevPi collects data from sensors and valves, publishing it to specific MQTT topics. The broker acts as an intermediary, distributing the data to clients that subscribe to the relevant topics. The user interface subscribes to these topics, enabling real-time display of sensor data and valve statuses. Additionally, it can send commands to the RevPi by publishing messages to control system actuators, such as valves. This two-way communication ensures seamless monitoring and control of the system.

The user interface for managing the system is designed to provide intuitive and immediate control over plant sensor readings and manual operations. To enhance clarity, the layout separates monitoring functions from active controls. On the central and left-hand sides of Figure 5, sensor readings are displayed in analogue gauge formats and dynamic graphs, offering real-time visualization of critical variables such as inlet water pressure, internal tank pressure, and water level. The gauges provide a quick view of current values, while the graphs track these metrics over time, enabling easy identification of trends or anomalies.

Figure 4. The communication structure of the experimental plant.

Figure 5. User interface for the plant management.

The command console is located on the right side of the interface, divided into three main sections. The top section allows the operator to set reference values for the PID controls, regulating inlet water pressure, internal tank pressure, and water level. This section enables configuration of target values required for maintaining optimal operating conditions. The middle section is dedicated to adjusting the PID constants, where the proportional, integral, and derivative parameters can be fine-tuned to

optimize system stability and response. Finally, the manual valve control interface is located at the bottom of the console. Here, the operator can directly manage the valves, controlling water inflow and outflow from the tank, providing immediate manual control when necessary or during maintenance.

An additional button on the interface enables the operator to log and store all activities and events occurring during system operation. This feature maintains a detailed history, capturing data such as sensor readings, PID adjustments, and manual valve operations.

3. THE DIGITAL TWINS REALIZATION AND THEIR INTEGRATION

3.1. Cyber-Physical digital twin modelling

The experimental plant is composed of two main models: the pump-ejector and vertical tank. At now, the integration of the pump-ejector and vertical tank models ensures that the system operates effectively by regulating water flow, pressure, and levels. The pump-ejector model simulates the relationship between water pressure and the airflow required to create the necessary suction for transport. As the system progresses, it continuously predicts the water pressure at the next time step based on the current values of relevant variables. These predictions, combined with the control of the solenoid valves, ensure that the water and air flow rates remain optimal.

Similarly, the vertical tank model is responsible for predicting and controlling the water level and internal pressure. Once the tank's level and pressure are estimated, the model uses this data to adjust the flow rates accordingly, ensuring that the pressure and level stay within the desired range. The PID controllers regulate the water and air outlet valves based on these predictions. As the water level rises, one valve opens to release water, while the other adjusts to maintain pressure. These actions are interdependent, meaning changes to one valve can affect the other.

The interaction between the tank and the ejector is another key element. As the water level and internal pressure of the tank change, they influence the flow and pressure of the mixture entering the tank. An increase in internal pressure can hinder the ejector ability to maintain the necessary flow rate, while changes in the water level can alter the density of the mixture, impacting the ejector's performance. This creates a feedback loop where the tank's behavior influences the ejector and vice versa, requiring synchronized control to maintain the system efficiency. The control system main goal is to maintain a balance between the water level and pressure within the tank. Through continuous adjustments made by the PID controllers, the system ensures that both variables remain within optimal limits. This requires constant monitoring and fine-tuning of the outlet flow rates to accommodate any fluctuations in the system. Since the tank behavior impacts the ejector performance, the entire system relies on coordinated control to ensure stable and efficient operation.

To further enhance the system adaptability, real-time model updating techniques will be essential. These methods, such as machine learning algorithms or Kalman filtering, allow the system to adjust to new operating conditions as they arise, ensuring that it can continuously optimize its performance. These techniques enable the system to learn from minimal sensor data and adapt its predictions accordingly, making it more responsive to dynamic changes in the operating environment.

3.2.3 Data analysis tool

Attributing semantic significance to the operator’s spatial position over time is a critical aspect of the analysis. To this purpose, the framework of Control Volumes (CVs) is employed. A CV refers to a defined three-dimensional region of arbitrary size and shape that can be positioned anywhere within the plant, typically corresponding to key zones or pieces of equipment. To identify when an operator is engaged within a specific area or interacting with designated equipment, a presence condition is established. This condition is met when the spatial coordinates of selected body sensors fall within the boundaries of the corresponding CV. In the context of this data collection campaign, the criterion for confirming the operator’s presence within a CV required that both feet and the pelvis sensors be located inside their spatial limits (but the script asks the user to select which joints to use as the verifying condition). Because of this and because of the closeness of the different CVs only CVs shaped as parallelepipeds were used.

An illustrative example of CV definition is in Figure 7: the first row specifies the CV’s identifier, followed by the x, y, and z origin coordinates in rows two to four. Rows five to seven detail the CV’s dimensions along the respective axes, while the final row indicates the cumulative time the operator spent within that CV.

By using the right number of CVs it is possible to extract important data regarding the operator’s work inside the plant. A MATLAB script allows better understanding of the operator’s performance and behavior by analyzing the dataset, as shown in Figure 8.

Once selected the dataset to be checked and the joints to use as the presence condition, the script checks for each frame if the (x,y,z) coordinates of each selected sensor are included in the boundaries of each CV (they could be nested one inside the other). If the check is positive, the “active” time spent on the CV is increased of a quantity of 0.33 seconds (the duration of the frame). The most important output of this process is the sequence of the CVs visited during the scenario and the respective times of each visit. Another significant output is the total time spent on each CV and the distance (over time) between the operator and each CV.

	A	B	C
1	Control Room	Control Panel	Water Reservoir
2	-2600	6950	-5520
3	0	0	0
4	-400	3200	0
5	3000	900	2710
6	1500	1500	1500
7	3920	1000	2020
8	0	0	0

Figure 7. Control Volumes definition example.

Figure 8. Analysis script flowchart.

3.2.4 Human digital twin from single actions

Based on the recordings, it is possible to identify the fundamental actions performed by the operator during the working activities. These basic actions can subsequently be recorded individually, creating a dataset of single actions, and, later, used to develop a fully digital scenario for the operator by concatenating the single actions needed via script. In this way there can be two different ways of monitoring the operator's performance, both by physically recording "live" actions and by digitally

replicating them starting from single basic actions. This kind of fully digital dataset can as well be an input to the MATLAB script to extract the crucial data.

3.3. The Human-Hardware-in-the-Loop digital twin

From the hardware and software integration point of view, the system architecture integrates two distinct Digital Twins: one representing the physical plant, developed in Python, and the other modelling the operator's behavior, developed in MATLAB. These components are connected through a dedicated integration layer that enables seamless communication and coordination. The plant DT simulates the dynamic behavior of the system and exposes key process variables.

When certain predefined conditions occur, the plant DT triggers specific messages to the operator DT, initiating a simulated decision-making process. The operator DT then processes the received information, evaluates the situation, and responds with appropriate control actions. These actions are fed back into the plant DT, effectively modifying the behavior of the system in real time. The integration layer ensures synchronization and data exchange, allowing both Digital Twins to operate coherently and adaptively in response to various operational scenarios. The overall DT works as it follows:

[Plant DT (Python)] → [State Message] → [Middleware/API] → [Operator DT (MATLAB)]
[Operator DT] → [Action Decision] → [Middleware/API] → [Plant DT]

In preparation for the experimental trials, a STAMP (Systems-Theoretic Accident Model and Processes) analysis is conducted on the plant to identify critical and realistic scenarios with potential safety implications. This methodology allows for a systematic evaluation of possible failure modes and unsafe control actions, offering a comprehensive understanding of how various components, both technical and human, interact to produce hazardous states. Following this initial analysis, a selection process filters scenarios based on two main criteria: the level of operator involvement and the feasibility of safely replicating the scenario under controlled experimental conditions. Scenarios are retained only if they involve substantial operator participation and can be simulated without posing risks to either the plant infrastructure or the personnel involved.

Once the filtering process is completed, the selected scenarios are further detailed in terms of the specific malfunction dynamics to be reproduced, and the corresponding operator actions required to detect and manage the anomalies. This preparatory phase ensures that both the technical parameters and human interactions are clearly defined, thereby enhancing the relevance and reliability of the experimental data to be collected. A series of experimental campaigns then follows during which the plant simulates the predefined malfunctions. During these sessions, the operator executes a structured set of responses aimed at identifying the anomaly and restoring normal operational conditions, while wearing a motion capture (MoCap) suit. The use of MoCap enables the capture of high-resolution behavioral data alongside system performance metrics, offering valuable insights into human-system interactions during abnormal events. The collected data serves to assess the effectiveness of current

procedures, identify potential areas for improvement, and ultimately support the enhancement of overall system safety and resilience.

4. THE ANALYZED CRITICAL SCENARIOS

In industrial systems equipped with process automation, ensuring the reliability of sensor readings is critical to maintaining stable and safe operations. To explore the effects of faulty measurements on system behavior, two critical scenarios were simulated. These scenarios focus on evaluating the system's response to persistent sensor anomalies – specifically, a false low reading of tank pressure and a false low reading of tank level.

Each scenario is structured in five consecutive phases, including normal operation, the introduction of the anomaly, system response through PID control, transition to a safe mode, full shutdown for inspection, and eventual recovery. The aim is to analyze the dynamics of the system under faulty conditions and to observe the effectiveness of control strategies and safety procedures in mitigating the risk of failure. Specifically:

1. *Scenario 1. False Low Reading of Tank Pressure:*

- a. *Normal Operation.* The system operates under stable conditions with all variables well-regulated and PID controllers active;
- b. *Anomaly (False Low Tank Pressure).* The tank pressure sensor provides a falsely low reading. The AV3 PID responds by opening the valve (reducing its closure) to increase pressure, leading to internal overpressure. AV1 remains stable, and the inlet air flow drops critically due to excessive internal pressure, which hinders the ejector ability to draw air;
- c. *Safe Mode.* The operator disables the PID controllers, freezing the valve positions and stabilizing the system in a safe state.
- d. *System Shutdown.* The plant is fully shut down to allow for safe inspection and maintenance operations;
- e. *System Restart.* The system is restarted, PID control is reactivated, and all variables return to stable, nominal behavior;

2. *Scenario 2. False Low Reading of Tank Level:*

- a. *Normal Operation.* The system is stable and well regulated, with all process variables within their desired ranges;
- b. *Anomaly (False Low Tank Level).* The tank level sensor reports a falsely low value. The AV2 PID reacts by closing the valve more (increasing the percentage of closure) to retain water, but the actual level keeps rising. AV3 compensates for the resulting overpressure by opening, keeping tank pressure stable. Inlet air flow remains steady due to the effective pressure control;

- c. *Safe Mode*. The operator disables the PID controllers to prevent further erroneous actions and stabilizes the system;
- d. *System Shutdown*. The system is completely turned off to allow for maintenance and anomaly assessment;
- e. *System Restart*. The system is brought back to standard operating conditions, with PID control restored and all variables behaving normally.

4.1. The experimental plant DT critical scenarios simulation with no integration

In the following sections, the critical scenarios under evaluation were simulated without integrating the operator's Digital Twin (DT). Each phase of the scenarios was simulated independently, with a duration of 5000 samples per phase, resulting in a total of 25,000 samples for each complete simulation to allow an in-depth comprehension of the plant simulated behavior.

Specifically, each phase consists of the same number of samples. From sample 1 to 5000, the system operates under normal conditions, with all variables stable and the PID controllers actively regulating the process. Between samples 5001 and 10000, an anomaly is introduced: either the tank pressure or the tank level sensor provides a continuously false low reading. This faulty measurement affects the behavior of the corresponding control loop, triggering an incorrect response from the system. From sample 10001 to 15000, the operator intervenes by disabling all PID controllers, placing the system in a safe mode to prevent further misregulation. In the following interval, from 15001 to 20000, the plant is fully shut down to allow safe inspection and maintenance activities. Finally, from sample 20001 to 25000, the system is restarted under standard operating conditions, with PID control restored and all process variables returning to normal behavior. This structure ensures that each phase is equally represented, allowing for a clear analysis of system dynamics across all stages.

4.1.1. Scenario 1

During the first 5000 samples, the system operates under stable conditions. All sensor readings and valve behaviors are consistent with a properly functioning plant. The inlet water pressure (Figure 9) and flow rate (Figure 10) are precisely controlled, ensuring a steady water supply to the tank. Similarly, the internal tank pressure (Figure 11) and level (Figure 12) follow regular trends, while the inlet air flow rate (Figure 13) confirms the effective operation of the ejector system. The control valves AV1, AV2, and AV3 (Figure 14 - Figure 16), which represent the percentage of valve closure, adjust dynamically and smoothly, without exhibiting instability or overcompensation.

Between samples 5001 and 10000, an anomaly emerges due to a false reading of the tank pressure. The S5 sensor (Figure 11) reports artificially low values, causing the control system to erroneously interpret the situation as a pressure deficit. As a result, the system reacts improperly: the tank pressure control valve AV3 reduces its percentage of closure (i.e., opens more) to increase what it mistakenly believes to be low pressure. Meanwhile, the inlet water pressure (Figure 9) remains constant, with AV1 maintaining a steady degree of closure, which prevents it from contributing effectively to pressure correction. This leads to unstable water flow (Figure 10) and tank level (Figure 12). Most

critically, the inlet air flow rate (Figure 5) drops sharply. This is due to the increasing internal pressure of the tank, which poses a serious constraint on the ejector. While the inlet water pressure is theoretically sufficient to overcome this constraint, the pressure drop inside the tank is not adequate to allow air suction from the outside. As a result, the air supply is cut off, further unbalancing the process.

Recognizing the abnormal behavior, the operator intervenes between samples 10001 and 15000 by manually shutting down the PID controllers, placing the system in a safe state. This action is immediately reflected in the valve: Trends (Figure 14 - Figure 16), which stabilize at fixed positions, and in the sensor readings (Figure 9 - Figure 13), which become steadier in the absence of active regulation. The objective during this phase is to protect the system from further mis regulation and to prepare for technical inspection. Subsequently, under safe and controlled conditions, the operator shuts down the plant completely to carry out diagnostic and maintenance procedures, aiming to identify the source of the anomaly and restore proper functionality.

From 15001 to 20000, the system remains fully shut down. All signals drop to zero or stabilize at constant values, consistent with a system in complete standstill. This maintenance window is essential to ensure safety and to perform the necessary repairs without risk.

In the final 5000 samples, the system is gradually restarted. The PID controllers are reactivated, and the valves resume modulating their closure levels in response to actual process conditions. All measurements – pressure, flow rates, and levels – progressively return to stable and expected values. This successful recovery indicates that the system has been fully restored to its standard operating condition, and that the corrective actions were effective in rebalancing the process.

Figure 9. Trend of sensor S1 (inlet water pressure) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank pressure (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 10. Trend of sensor S2 (inlet water flow rate) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank pressure (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 11. Trend of sensor S5 (tank pressure) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank pressure (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 12. Trend of sensor S6 (tank level) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank pressure (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 13. Trend of sensor S7 (inlet air flow rate) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank pressure (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 14. Trend of the valve AV1 (valve for the inlet water pressure control) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank pressure (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 15. Trend of the valve AV2 (valve for the tank level control) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank pressure (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 16. Trend of the valve AV3 (valve for the tank pressure control) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank pressure (from sample 5000 to 10000).

4.1.2. Scenario 2

During the first 5000 samples, the system operates in a stable and balanced condition. All key variables – inlet water pressure (Figure 17), water flow rate (Figure 18), tank pressure (Figure 19), tank level (Figure 20), and inlet air flow (Figure 21) – follow regular trends. Control valves – AV1 (inlet water pressure), AV2 (tank level), and AV3 (tank pressure) – adjust their percentages of closure dynamically (Figure 22 - Figure 24) to maintain equilibrium through PID control.

Between samples 5001 and 10000, an anomaly occurs due to a continuous false low reading of the tank level from sensor S6 (Figure 20). The PID controlling AV2 receives this incorrect information at every instant, interpreting that the tank is underfilled. As a result, AV2 increases its closure percentage – closing more – to retain water and raise the level. However, since the reading remains falsely low, the controller never considers the level sufficient, and the tank continues to fill beyond the actual target.

Interestingly, the inlet water flow rate (Figure 18) remains unchanged, indicating that the anomaly does not cause increased input. Instead, the water accumulates due to reduced outflow through the increasingly closed AV2. This leads to a rise in internal tank pressure.

To manage the growing pressure, AV3 (the tank pressure control valve) decreases its closure percentage – opening more – to release the excess pressure and keep the tank stable (Figure 24). This action is effective: as shown in Figure 19, the tank pressure remains stable, without any sharp increase.

Consequently, the inlet air flow (Figure 21) also remains stable, since the pressure differential required for air aspiration is maintained. Minor oscillations may occur, but there is no collapse in air intake, thanks to AV3's compensation action that keeps internal pressure under control.

From 10001 to 15000 samples, the operator switches off all PID controllers, placing the system in safe mode. The valves (Figure 22 - Figure 24) maintain fixed closure positions, and sensor readings (Figure 17 - Figure 21) stabilize, indicating that the system is no longer being actively regulated.

Between samples 15001 and 20000, the system is fully shut down. All values flatten or drop to zero, reflecting a complete stop for inspection and maintenance.

In the final 5000 samples, the system is restarted under standard operating conditions. The PID loops are re-enabled, the control valves resume dynamic behavior, and all key variables return to normal values. This confirms that the system has recovered and is once again functioning correctly.

Please note how Figure 21 shows that, since there is still a significant amount of water in the tank, when the PID is turned off, the rising transient that marks the resumption of air suction does not exhibit the same overshoot during the transition from system off to system on.

Figure 17. Trend of sensor S1 (inlet water pressure) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank level (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 18. Trend of sensor S2 (inlet water flow rate) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank level (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 19. Trend of sensor S5 (tank pressure) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank level (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 20. Trend of sensor S6 (tank level) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank level (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 21. Trend of sensor S7 (inlet air flow rate) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank level (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 22. Trend of the valve AV1 (valve for the inlet water pressure control) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank level (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 23. Trend of the valve AV2 (valve for tank pressure control) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank level (from sample 5000 to 10000).

Figure 24. Trend of the valve AV3 (valve for the tank level control) during the simulation of an incorrect reading of the vertical tank level (from sample 5000 to 10000).

4.2. The plant operator's DT scenarios simulation with no integration

The digitalized scenarios developed using the technologies outlined in Section 3.2 are detailed in this section, and intersect with the descriptions provided from the plant's perspective.

1. *Scenario 1. False Low Reading of Tank Pressure:*

a. Anomaly detection phase:

- i. The operator becomes aware of the problem due to the noise generated by the ejector, which is operating under abnormal conditions;
- ii. After verifying the operating conditions of the ejector, the operator shuts down the PID controllers from the Control Room and waits for approximately 30 seconds;
- iii. The operator shuts down the system either from the Control Room or directly from the Control Panel;

b. Restart phase:

- i. The operator positions himself near the system discharge point to verify proper drainage;
- ii. Proceeds to the Control Room to disconnect the power supply to the sensors;
- iii. Takes a wrench from the Work Bench;
- iv. Reaches sensor S5 to disassemble it;
- v. Brings the sensor to the Work Bench to perform a manual calibration;
- vi. Once the calibration is completed, the operator inputs the values into Excel in the Control Room to reset the Revpi;
- vii. The operator then reassembles the sensor in its original position;
- viii. Powers the sensors back on and restarts the system from the Control Room;

2. *Scenario 2. False Low Reading of Tank Level:*

a. Anomaly detection phase:

- i. The operator becomes aware of the problem due to the noise generated by the AV2, which is operating under abnormal conditions;
- ii. After verifying the operating conditions of AV2, the operator also checks the S1-S2 sensors and the outlet water transparent tube;
- iii. If all the check led to the confirmation of an issue, the operator shuts down the PID from the Control Room;
- iv. After waiting for circa 60 seconds, the operator turns off the plant from the Control Room or directly from the Control Panel;

b. Restart phase:

- i. The operator goes to the manual valve V2 to close it;
- ii. He then goes to the water reservoir to check the correct drainage of the plant;
- iii. After that, it is possible to restart the system from the Control Room.

For each part of every scenario, five recordings are collected. In addition, three simulations are conducted for each part of every scenario in which the system shutdown was performed from the Control Panel instead of from the Control Room. The results are shown in the next tables. In the tables, CVs are highlighted (in the order in which they were defined), as well as the times spent in each CV (expressed in seconds) for each take. Each row indicates which CV the operator is in, represented by a “1” digit (if there are no 1s, the operator is outside any CV, typically moving from one to another).

The first row for both Table 2 and Table 3 refers to the time that passes before the operator hears the noise and represents the most variable parameter. This is valid also for the Anomaly detection phase in Scenario 2.

Table 2. Scenario 1 - Anomaly detection - Shut down from Control Panel

<i>Control Room</i>	<i>Control Panel</i>	<i>Ejector</i>	<i>Time [s] – Take 1</i>	<i>Time [s] – Take 2</i>	<i>Time [s] – Take 3</i>
1			14.97	40.38	7.87
			3.97	4.14	4.21
		1	9.09	12.29	8.49
			4.27	5.01	3.78
1			31.05	25.32	30.54
			6.78	6.64	6.27
	1		8.59	9.17	8.85

Table 3. Scenario 1 - Anomaly detection - Shut down from Control Room

<i>Control Room</i>	<i>Ejector</i>	<i>Time [s] – Take 1</i>	<i>Time [s] – Take 2</i>	<i>Time [s] – Take 3</i>	<i>Time [s] – Take 4</i>	<i>Time [s] – Take 5</i>
1		33.63	12.76	20.93	18.91	37.61
		6.95	7.21	6.55	6.09	6.74
	1	5.88	3.71	3.40	5.64	5.41
		7.35	6.69	6.24	6.92	7.16
1		37.10	39.83	36.91	30.42	37.97

Table 4. Scenario 1 - Restart phase - From Control Panel

<i>Control Room</i>	<i>Control Panel</i>	<i>Water Reservoir</i>	<i>Work Bench</i>	<i>S5</i>	<i>Time [s] – Take 1</i>	<i>Time [s] – Take 2</i>	<i>Time [s] – Take 3</i>
	1				1.90	1.85	1.44
					8.78	8.55	8.57
		1			12.54	14.09	13.85
					3.22	5.48	2.80

1					9.94	4.74	8.19
					1.32	4.60	4.13
			1		4.08	1.74	1.58
					4.76	6.00	3.41
				1	376.12	468.85	350.84
					5.69	6.14	7.29
			1		536.44	400.20	514.66
					4.86	3.24	4.06
1					357.59	180.41	235.32
					1.18	1.67	0.54
				1	395.58	419.28	276.07
					2.07	1.19	0.65
1					11.59	6.38	8.98

Table 5. Scenario 1 - Restart phase - From Control Room

Control Room	Water Reservoir	Work Bench	S5	Time [s] – Take 1	Time [s] – Take 2	Time [s] – Take 3	Time [s] – Take 4	Time [s] – Take 5
1				3.02	2.29	2.31	2.29	1.98
				4.32	5.01	4.40	4.75	4.06
	1			5.45	17.35	21.24	17.52	13.78
				4.08	4.17	6.25	5.14	3.51
1				4.36	4.55	5.52	5.81	5.15
				3.00	3.20	2.79	2.67	2.63
		1		3.21	0.97	4.02	2.74	2.97
				2.64	2.92	5.52	5.56	2.56
			1	282.50	281.11	307.25	309.75	488.31
				5.11	5.01	6.25	5.56	5.63
		1		535.40	378.31	326.98	430.44	307.75
				3.88	3.72	3.98	3.24	4.13
1				469.87	435.43	612.88	589.56	378.49
				0.89	2.68	3.35	3.27	2.52
			1	268.88	272.41	319.64	340.08	440.80
				2.68	2.99	3.00	3.10	2.93
1				7.38	7.82	7.65	7.85	7.37

Table 6. Scenario 2- Anomaly detection - Shut down from Control Panel

Control Room	Control Panel	SI_S2	AV2	Water Outlet	Time [s] – Take 1	Time [s] – Take 2	Time [s] – Take 3
1					12.47	16.01	13.55
					1.51	1.51	0.96
			1		6.87	8.74	8.77
					5.57	5.28	5.15
		1			4.40	5.07	7.54
					5.81	6.14	5.84
				1	7.28	6.27	7.24
					1.03	1.95	1.40
1					43.40	49.79	49.76

					7.99	6.69	8.29
	1				7.35	9.77	7.17

Table 7. Scenario 2- Anomaly detection - Shut down from Control Room

Control Room	S1_S2	AV2	Water Outlet	Time [s] – Take 1	Time [s] – Take 2	Time [s] – Take 3	Time [s] – Take 4	Time [s] – Take 5
1				29.68	11.95	17.17	16.61	24.59
				3.62	2.36	2.65	2.59	2.35
		1		5.95	10.53	8.55	7.35	7.82
				5.64	4.40	4.92	5.11	4.84
	1			5.81	7.51	8.27	8.67	7.71
				5.98	5.06	4.78	5.01	4.73
			1	4.62	7.55	8.27	7.77	8.78
				3.28	1.87	0.81	0.90	1.14
1				61.34	67.03	65.48	65.67	63.82

Table 8. Scenario 2 - Restart phase - From Control Panel

Control Room	Control Panel	Water Reservoir	Manual Valve	Time [s] – Take 1	Time [s] – Take 2	Time [s] – Take 3
	1			0.68	1.41	0.51
				6.11	5.98	6.34
			1	2.40	2.60	4.25
				6.63	6.12	7.01
		1		7.83	9.33	7.82
				4.69	3.82	4.18
1				2.09	3.96	2.67

Table 9. Scenario 2 - Restart phase - From Control Room

Control Room	Water Reservoir	Manual Valve	Time [s] – Take 1	Time [s] – Take 2	Time [s] – Take 3	Time [s] – Take 4	Time [s] – Take 5
1			2.27	1.84	2.23	2.17	1.87
			2.91	1.06	0.57	1.12	1.05
		1	5.05	3.86	4.55	4.47	3.33
			4.08	5.23	4.91	5.48	5.54
	1		11.62	11.40	11.73	11.31	10.41
			2.81	3.21	1.99	3.15	3.27
1			4.23	3.28	3.54	2.78	2.96

As we can see benchmarking the different takes of each scenario, the times spent for each action are comparable. The biggest differences are found in the Restart phase of Scenario 1, where the operator has to perform the most difficult and time-consuming operations.

All those outputs are then fed to the combined DT to extract the overall resilience performance of the CSTS.

4.3. The Human-Hardware-in-the-Loop scenarios simulation

The final phase of the system's DT development involved integrating the two separate DTs (i.e., one representing the physical plant and the other the human operator) into a unified Human-Hardware-in-the-Loop Digital Twin (HHIL DT). The first step in this integration was identifying the specific time periods during which the human operator could influence the plant's performance.

In the simulation plots (see Figures 9 - 24), recurring patterns can be observed across different runs. These patterns align with distinct phases of plant operation, as illustrated in Figure 25, and can be categorized as it follows:

1. *Steady-state.* At the beginning of the simulation, the plant operates under steady-state conditions (grey zone in Figure 25), with no cyber-attacks occurring. Since the simulations assume that a cyber-attack will eventually succeed, this phase offers no opportunity for operator intervention. Therefore, operator-related data is not relevant or included in this stage;
2. *Under attack.* At a certain point, a cyber-attack begins to affect the plant's performance (red zone in Figure 25). For example, in Figure 25, the water level in the tank (measured by sensor S6) starts rising abnormally. During this phase, the operator's role is to detect the anomaly as early as possible. The operator's detection time directly influences the length of this phase: the sooner the operator identifies the attack, the quicker they can initiate shutdown procedures and begin corrective actions;
3. *Shutdown.* Once the attack is identified, the plant enters a shutdown phase (orange zone in Figure 25), where performance rapidly declines to zero. Although the duration of this phase is not directly governed by operator behavior within it, it is indirectly affected by how quickly the operator reacted in the previous phase. For instance, in the scenario shown in Figure 25, the adversary managed to raise the water level to approximately 650 mm before shutdown began. Had the operator responded earlier, the tank would have contained less water, and the shutdown process would have been faster;
4. *Plant off.* After shutdown, the plant remains off, entering a new, unintended but stable state (green zone in Figure 25). During this period, the operator must assess the system, investigate potential compromises (e.g., sensor tampering), and perform necessary recalibrations or diagnostics. The length of this phase is directly tied to the duration of the operator's intervention: the faster these tasks are completed, the sooner the plant can resume operations;
5. *Start-up.* Once all recovery and verification activities are complete, the operator initiates the start-up process (blue zone in Figure 25). The plant then transitions back to its original steady-state. Since this phase is largely automated, the operator has no influence over its duration. Thus, operator data is not included for this phase either.

To summarize, integrating the two DTs into a single HHIL DT resulted in linking operator's data as it follows:

1. The duration of the Under attack phase depends on the operator's detection ability. Specifically, the time taken to recognize the anomaly and initiate plant shutdown. This duration is calculated by summing (row by row) the time values reported in Tables 2 - 3 and Tables 6 - 7;

2. While the Shutdown phase duration itself is not directly influenced by operator actions during this phase, it is indirectly affected by the detection time. The state of the plant at the end of the detection period determines the starting point of the shutdown profile;
3. The length of the Plant off phase is driven by the operator's restoration capacity, that is, the time required to complete all recovery tasks and prepare the plant for restart. This is measured by summing (row by row) the time values in Tables 4 - 5 and Tables 8 - 9.

Figure 25. Trend of the sensor S6 in simulation scenario 1 (exemplary) with periods of interest highlighted.

On this basis, to accurately simulate plant behavior under cyber-attack conditions while incorporating the variability of human intervention, a MATLAB script was developed to integrate data into the HHIL DT. This procedure allows the system to reflect different operator responses across the phases of detection and restoration, producing a modified plant performance profile that captures the dynamics of human-influenced behavior.

The process begins with the selection of the specific attack scenario to be simulated. Each scenario represents a predefined sequence of plant behavior under cyber-attack, stored in the workspace as either *scenario1Table* or *scenario2Table*. These are the data obtained from the Hardware-in-the-Loop simulations.

Once a scenario is chosen, the system introduces variability by randomly determining whether to incorporate operator data that includes Control Panel based interactions or not. This choice reflects differences in how operators engage with the system shutdown, whether through direct on-site controls or remote interfaces (see Section 4.2 for details).

Next, the code randomly selects a specific operator take for the detection phase. The takes are drawn from a set of pre-recorded temporal sequences, and they are stored in the workspace as *temporalSequence_Dn_Tm* or *temporalSequence_Dn_Tm_CP*, where *n* defines the scenario (either 1 or 2), *m* defines the specific take (either 1 to 3 or 1 to 5), and *CP* identify control panel-related scenarios. These data are the results from the Human-in-the-Loop simulations, and they provide a realistic measurement of how long a human operator takes to identify an ongoing anomaly. A similar process is used to select a take for the restoration phase, which reflects the operator's recovery actions after shutting the plant down.

From the selected sequences, two key durations are extracted: the detection time and the restoration time. These times are then used to tailor the simulation profiles for the plant behavior accordingly.

Indeed, the next step involves identifying the distinct operational phases within the scenario table: Steady-state, Under attack, Shutdown, Plant off, and Start-up. Based on the detection time, the script trims the Under attack phase, retaining only the portion of the time series that corresponds to the duration required for the operator to detect the anomaly. Then, similarly, the Plant off phase is trimmed according to the restoration time, reflecting the time needed for the operator to complete system recovery tasks and prepare for restart.

The Shutdown phase requires a more nuanced adjustment. Since, as discussed above, the shutdown shall begin at the moment detection ends, the script calculates the point in the shutdown phase that is closest – in terms of the Euclidean distance in the feature space – to the last point of the before trimmed Under attack phase. All preceding data points in the shutdown phase are removed, ensuring a coherent and continuous transition between detection and shutdown periods.

Figure 26 include an example input/output of the script logics illustrated above, related to the level of water in the tank (i.e., S6) in a simulation for the second scenario. It is possible to notice how (e.g.) the duration of the Plant off phase (i.e., period in which the water level is approximately 200 mm) is clearly shorter in the plot on the right.

Figure 26. Trend of the sensor S6 in simulation scenario 1 (exemplary) before and after the integration with human-related data.

5. CONCLUSION

This report has outlined the methodology developed to integrate data from both Hardware-in-the-Loop and Human-in-the-Loop simulations, capturing the interaction between plant processes and human operator behavior. A detailed description of the data structures was provided, along with a comprehensive explanation of the MATLAB script designed to generate integrated performance profiles. These profiles reflect not only the physical dynamics of the plant under cyber-attack scenarios but also the variable influence of humans during the critical intervention periods.

The principal output of WP5100 is a collection of plant performance trajectories that explicitly incorporate operator behavior. These are not limited to a fixed dataset; rather, the developed computational framework was built with scalability and reproducibility in mind. This means that the system can be readily expanded to include additional operator trials or attack scenarios, thereby enabling the continuous generation of new performance profiles without requiring substantial

changes to the underlying code. More broadly, this work contributes to the overarching goals of WP5000, which aims to assess system-level resilience within a cyber-socio-technical framework. Once integrated performance profiles are available, various methods can be employed to quantify resilience. For this project, and as further discussed in Deliverable D2000-C (i.e., Technical Report on Cyber Threats and Draft Resilience Metrics Based on the STAMP Model), resilience is to be evaluated using a comparative area-based approach. Specifically, resilience is defined as the ratio between the area under the curve representing normal plant operations and the area under the curve depicting the disrupted state due to cyber incidents. This metric, while straightforward in concept, provides valuable insight into how different operator behaviors (i.e., detection speed and restoration efficiency) impact the overall system resilience, highlighting the role of the human performance as a critical factor in shaping the plant's ability to respond to and recover from cyber threats.

Nonetheless, several challenges must be addressed to ensure accurate and meaningful resilience evaluation. Potential issues include: (i) differing time horizons between normal and disrupted operation datasets, which can lead to non-comparable area values; (ii) misalignment in the timing of key events across performance profiles, which can artificially inflate or reduce perceived differences; and (iii) excessively long time series that obscure meaningful variations by including extended periods of overlap between phases. These and other related concerns will be systematically addressed in the subsequent work packages dedicated to resilience metric refinement and validation. Despite these anticipated adjustments, the integration procedure described in this report represents a critical foundation for the project's final objectives. It establishes a robust and extensible framework that bridges human and system-level data, laying the groundwork for a rigorous, data-driven assessment of resilience in complex cyber-socio-technical systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) – Mission 4 Education and Research – Component 2 From research to business - Investment 1.1, Prin 2022 Notice announced with DD No. 104 of 2/2/2022, entitled RESIST - RESilience management to Industrial Systems Threats, proposal code 2022YSAE2X